

Nuclear Data Uncertainties in TAPIRO for Fast Reactor Design - a testimony to Mario Carta achievements

V. Fabrizio^{1*}, P. Blaise², A. Santagata¹, L. Falconi¹, L. Lepore¹, V. Peluso³

¹ENEA, C.R. Casaccia, Via Anguillarese, 301, Rome, Italy;

²Framatome, DTIPD, WIP 2 rue Prof J. Bernard, 69007 Lyon, France;

³ENEA, C.R. Bologna, via Martiri di Monte Sole, 4 – 40129 Bologna, Italy.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803440

ABSTRACT

In all the research activities to which Mario Carta has made significant contributions, TAPIRO has always played a central role, focusing on the development of experiments to support the international scientific community of Reactor Physicists. One of the last proposals Mario Carta put forward within the NEA group of experts he collaborated with, was the idea of conducting integral experiments with minor actinides in TAPIRO, to reduce uncertainties in cross-section nuclear data. This idea gave rise to the AOSTA (Activation of OSMOSE Sample in TAPIRO reactor) experimental program, a collaboration between ENEA and CEA. This program, despite a temporary stop, remains ongoing. Among the activities carried out for AOSTA, feasibility studies were conducted on sensitivity and uncertainty analyses of the reference spectral indices of selected nuclear reactions, in the light of the design of future lead-cooled fast reactors. In this paper, the k_{eff} sensitivity analysis with both deterministic and Monte Carlo methodologies has been compared, and some selected spectral indices have been considered to evaluate the effective contribution of TAPIRO to current fast-reactors design challenges. The paper reports also on the first experimental set-up and characterization realized for the most promising irradiation point, focusing on the principal activation channel for actinide activation analysis.

Keywords: TAPIRO, Advanced Fast reactors, Nuclear Data, representativity

1. INTRODUCTION

In the design of current and future nuclear fast reactors, the quantification of uncertainties plays a crucial role in almost all parts of the fuel cycle, reducing the risks, enhancing knowledge of safety and security margins, and minimizing the production of nuclear waste. Nuclear data uncertainty is a significant factor in the design and safety analysis of lead-cooled fast reactors (LFRs), as it directly affects the accuracy of simulations for parameters like the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}). Quantifying and propagating these uncertainties are major issues for demonstrating reactor safety. Sensitivity and uncertainty analysis can be employed to understand the impact of uncertainties in nuclear data on LFR performance. Reducing nuclear data uncertainty, which is crucial for neutronic design, involves a combination of experimental and computational improvements, including designing more precise experiments and utilizing advanced analysis techniques. These goals remain challenging, particularly for fast reactors, especially when their fuels are heavily loaded with minor actinides.

Minor actinides (MAs), such as americium (Am), neptunium (Np), and curium (Cm) isotopes, play a significant role in the fuel cycle of advanced nuclear reactors, especially fast reactors and those designed for transmutation. However, the nuclear data associated with these isotopes (e.g., neutron cross sections, fission yields, decay data) often suffer from large uncertainties due to limited experimental measurements and complex nuclear behavior.

An international Expert Group, supported by the Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA), has established the High Priority Request List (HPRL) which includes a list of requested nuclear data improvements for high-priority isotopes and reactions of interest.

The RSV TAPIRO (TARatura Pila Rapida a Potenza 0) [1] is a fast neutron source reactor, located at ENEA Casaccia Center, that represents almost the unique opportunity to have experiments dedicated to nuclear data reduction uncertainties in fission neutron energy domain within Europe. Conducting

tailored experiments in TAPIRO, which provide fast neutron spectra similar to those in fast reactors, allows for benchmarking and validation of MAs nuclear data [2].

In this work a preliminary characterization of one position of the TAPIRO tangential channel and the k_{eff} sensitivity and uncertainty evaluations of the TAPIRO main isotopes, by means of the Standard Perturbation Theory (SPT) [3] and by both deterministic and Monte Carlo methodologies, are presented. Sensitivities and uncertainties, via the Generalized Perturbation Theory (GPT) [4,5,6], of some selected spectral indexes, involved in MAs nuclear data uncertainty reduction, have been analyzed and discussed to determine which data improvements would have the most significant impact on future LFR core parameters.

2. RSV TAPIRO RESEARCH REACTOR AND COMPUTATIONAL MODELS

2.1. TAPIRO reactor description

TAPIRO (TARatura Pila Rapida a Potenza 0) is a fast neutron source reactor licensed in 1971, developed by ENEA's staff, based on the general concept of AFSR (Argonne Fast Source Reactor - Idaho Falls). The nominal power of the reactor is 5 kW. Since 1971, it has been used for fast reactor shielding experiments, biological effects of fast neutrons, electronic component neutron damage, etc.

The reactor is made of a homogeneous uranium-molybdenum alloy (98.5 % U, 1.5 % Mo in weight). The cylindrical core, with about 6 cm of radius and 11 cm of height, is divided into two parts: the upper one is fixed to the reactor structure whereas the lower one is movable and can be dropped to rapidly shut-down the system [1]. A vertical and horizontal section of the reactor is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. TAPIRO vertical section (left) and horizontal section (right).

2.2. TAPIRO computational models

The TAPIRO fast research reactor was modeled by the deterministic code ERANOS 2.3 [6] to study k_{eff} sensitivity coefficients, and correlated uncertainties, by means of Standard Perturbation Theory (SPT) and by means Generalized Perturbation Theory (GPT) [2, 3, 4] for selected spectral indexes of interest to nuclear data uncertainty reduction.

The deterministic model of the system was developed using the RZ geometry: in this geometry, only the diametral experimental channel has been considered. All the parameters of interest have been evaluated along this diametral channel [2].

The ERANOS simulations have been performed with the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library [7], which has been processed and collapsed to 80 energy groups [8], translated into a special format readable by ERANOS.

3. k_{eff} Sensitivity and Uncertainty Evaluation

Evaluating the sensitivity of k_{eff} in nuclear theory involves using sensitivity and uncertainty analysis to understand how variations in nuclear data (like cross-sections) affect the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}). This is achieved by calculating sensitivity coefficients, which quantify the change in k_{eff} resulting from a given change in nuclear data. These coefficients are then combined with nuclear data covariance matrices to predict the overall uncertainty in k_{eff} .

SPT is used in k_{eff} sensitivity analysis. It consists of calculating the sensitivity coefficients S_{keff} of the multiplication factor k_{eff} to the parameter of interest P_i , as expressed by:

$$S_{keff} = \frac{\Delta k_{eff}/k_{eff}}{\Delta P_i/P_i} \quad (1)$$

k_{eff} sensitivity calculations in this study have been performed using the ERANOS code system [5], which enables the calculation of homogeneous and inhomogeneous solutions of the Boltzmann equation as well as generalized importance functions, perturbation and uncertainty analysis. These calculations were compared with the Monte Carlo MCNP [9] code simulations performed using adjoint-weighted methods. The MCNP simulations were carried out using the TAPIRO model described in [10] and 6.3 version of code.

The sensitivity coefficients include all isotopes and nuclear data, including cross sections, fission neutrons and spectra. The selected cross sections consider the following reactions: capture, fission, elastic and inelastic scattering, and (n,xn) and include all isotopes. The total value of the sensitivity coefficients summed over energy groups is shown in Figure 2.

Table I summarizes the contribution to the sensitivity coefficient (integrated over energy) from selected isotopes for the TAPIRO reactor. The sensitivity contribution from the capture cross section is always negative: the major contributor is the U-235, uranium and copper isotopes contribute most to the sensitivity and the major contribution from the elastic scattering cross section comes from Cu-63.

Table I. k_{eff} sensitivity coefficients from ERANOS and MCNP simulations for principal isotopes contribution: U-235, U-238, Cu-63, Cu64.

Isotope/ Reaction	U-235		U-238	
	ERANOS	MCNP	ERANOS	MCNP
CAPTURE	-5.69E - 02	-5.55E - 02	-2.33E - 03	-2.29E - 03
FISSION	6.13E - 01	6.12E - 01	6.30E - 03	6.30E - 03
ELASTIC	3.64E - 02	3.72E - 02	2.75E - 03	2.76E - 03
INEL.	4.86E - 02	4.35E - 02	4.23E - 03	3.76E - 03
N,XN	1.69E - 03	1.75E - 03	1.32E - 04	1.31E - 04
SUM	6.43E - 01	6.39E - 01	1.11E - 02	1.07E - 02

Isotope/ Reaction	Cu-63		Cu-65	
	ERANOS	MCNP	ERANOS	MCNP
CAPTURE	-2.31E - 02	-1.99E - 02	-5.62E - 03	-4.85E - 03
FISSION	0.00E + 00	0.00E + 00	0.00E + 00	0.00E + 00
ELASTIC	1.25E - 01	1.16E - 01	6.38E - 02	6.23E - 02
INEL.	2.97E - 02	2.35E - 02	1.11E - 02	8.79E - 03
N,XN	8.78E - 06	8.03E - 06	1.38E - 05	1.26E - 05
SUM	1.31E - 01	1.19E - 01	6.93E - 02	6.63E - 02

Table II reports the uncertainty of coefficients (Eq. 1) for selected isotopes and nuclear data.

Table II. k_{eff} uncertainty coefficients (%) from ERANOS for principal isotopes contributors.

Uncertainty Coefficients							
ISOTOPE	CAPTURE	FISSION	ELASTIC	INELASTIC	NU	N,XN	TOTAL
U-235	3.74E - 03	7.45E - 03	1.01E - 03	1.78E - 03	4.04E - 03	3.69E - 04	9.49E - 03
U-238	1.99E - 05	1.35E - 04	1.19E - 04	2.08E - 04	1.13E - 04	2.13E - 05	2.97E - 04
Cu-63	7.36E - 04	0.00E + 00	1.90E - 03	2.00E - 03	0.00E + 00	6.30E - 07	2.86E - 03
Cu-65	1.63E - 04	0.00E + 00	1.43E - 03	7.69E - 04	0.00E + 00	8.44E - 07	1.64E - 03
TOTAL	3.81E - 03	7.45E - 03	2.59E - 03	2.80E - 03	4.04E - 03	3.70E - 04	1.01E - 02

 Figure 2. TAPIRO k_{eff} sensitivity from all isotopes and nuclear data from ERANOS and MCNP and neutron energy spectrum in different reactor positions.

The total k_{eff} sensitivity coefficients, Figure 2 shows good agreement between the two codes and demonstrates that the simplified deterministic model well describes the TAPIRO reactor.

The sensitivity coefficients in Figure 2 are centered in the fast energy domain, implying that the TAPIRO reactor, having an energy spectrum limited to the fast zone, acts as a filter for the measurements performed on samples of interest for the reduction of nuclear data.

Furthermore, the TAPIRO reactor has a neutron spectrum that well represents the spectrum of fast reactors such as lead-cooled reactor as shown in [8], Figure 3 shows an example of spectral comparison in a position along the diametral channel at the interface between the copper reflector and the biological shield with the ALFRED neutron spectrum.

Figure 3. TAPIRO - ALFRED energy spectra comparison [8].

4. Sensitivity and Uncertainty Analysis for Selected Spectral Indexes

A sensitivity and uncertainty study has been conducted to assess the impact of neutron cross-section uncertainty on the most significant integral parameters associated with the TAPIRO core and reflector.

The Generalized Perturbation Theory (GPT) [3,4] is an extension of the Standard Perturbation Theory (SPT) to any linear functional of the neutron flux.

The uncertainty of a parameter (k_{eff} or spectral index) from cross sections can be derived by introducing the covariance matrix C. The total uncertainty on a parameter can be obtained from:

$$\varepsilon = \sqrt{S^T \cdot C \cdot S} \tag{1}$$

where S is the sensitivity coefficient array for all isotopes, cross sections and groups, calculated using either SPT for k_{eff} or GPT for SI.

The covariance matrix used in this work is based on the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library, except for copper isotopes data that have been retrieved from the JEFF-3.3 nuclear data library [11].

The selected spectral indexes for this work are:

- $^{239}\text{Pu}_{\text{fission}}/^{238}\text{U}_{\text{fission}}$, (labeled as F49/F28): it gives an indication of a total fission rate relative to the threshold fission rate of U-238; it is a good indicator of fission in a fast (sodium or lead) reactor,
- $^{237}\text{Np}_{\text{fission}}/^{238}\text{U}_{\text{fission}}$, (labeled as F27/F28); gives an indication of the epithermal threshold fission rate relative to the fast threshold fission rate of U-238; it is a good indicator of how much neptunium can be incinerated in a fast reactor,
- $^{235}\text{U}_{\text{fission}}/^{238}\text{U}_{\text{fission}}$, (labeled as F25/F28); gives an indication of a total fission rate relative to the threshold fission rate of U-238. It is similar to F49/F28 more suitable for uranium systems,
- $^{238}\text{U}_{\text{capture}}/^{235}\text{U}_{\text{fission}}$, (labeled as C28/F25). It is called conversion ratio as it gives the amount of Pu-239 produced per U-235 fission.

Figure 4 shows that the sensitivity coefficients for the F49/F25, F37/F28 and F25/F28 spectral indexes are relevant only in the fast region, while in the thermal and epithermal region, the sensitivity of the system is practically zero. This information, together with the uncertainty coefficients, predicts the feasibility of an experiment in TAPIRO that can lead to nuclear data uncertainties reduction in the fast domain.

Table III. Selected isotopes and nuclear data uncertainty contributions to the spectral indexes studied, at 25 cm from the core center.

Uncertainties coefficients						
S.I.	CAPTURE	FISSION	ELASTIC	INELASTIC	NU	N,XN
F49/F28	8.04E - 03	1.66E - 02	1.38E - 02	7.46E - 02	1.58E - 04	1.45E - 03
F37/F28	1.18E - 03	3.88E - 02	2.11E - 02	3.09E - 02	9.44E - 04	5.39E - 02
F25/F28	9.46E - 03	1.68E - 02	1.54E - 02	7.99E - 02	1.60E - 03	0.00E + 0
C28/F25	1.30E - 02	1.07E - 02	6.66E - 03	3.86E - 03	0.00E + 0	0.00E + 0

All the spectral indexes with the U-238 fission threshold reaction (F27/F28 and C28/F25), shown in Figures 4 b) and 5 exhibit similar patterns with high sensitivities in the high energy range, where the knowledge on nuclear data is low.

c)

Figure 4: Sensitivity coefficients for spectral indices (a: F49/F35, b: F37/F25, c: F25/F28) by ERANOS code

Figures 5 and Table VI illustrate the sensitivity and uncertainty coefficients of the C28/F25 spectral index relevant for Pu-239 breeder reactors operating in the epithermal/fast energy range and shows that for the goal of a strong reduction of the U-238 capture uncertainty, the TAPIRO reactor is suitable. TAPIRO presents higher uncertainty in the high energy range of interest for fast reactor applications.

Figure 5: Sensitivity coefficients for spectral index C28/F25 by ERANOS code.

5. Experimental Set-up

The diametrical channel of TAPIRO, going through the central part of the core, provides a relatively pure fission neutron spectrum. Then, the natural choice for cross-section measurement in the fission spectrum falls on this channel. Unfortunately, the diametrical channel is part of the reactor primary cooling system, and the use of the diametrical channel requires a specific procedure to maintain helium leakage below a prescribed level. Consequently, it is more realistic to consider another irradiation point. The tangential channel is not part of the primary circuit, and its utilization does not require the same restrictions as the diametrical channel. In this channel, the actinide can be introduced and removed easily, and a suitable neutron spectrum can be obtained. However, it is not close to the fission spectrum as in the diametrical channel, but it can be considered an acceptable approximation. For the procedure described in the previous paragraph, the experimental campaign consists of measuring the neutron spectrum at several meaningful positions along the tangential channel, irradiating actinide samples at these positions, and gamma-spectrometry of post-irradiated actinide samples. Calculations will be performed for estimating the neutron spectra, reaction rate of actinides, and irradiation time and power that provide, at the end of irradiation, a counting rate in the gamma spectrometry of the sample, sufficiently high to furnish a low

uncertainty level. The post-irradiation sample dose rate will also be estimated to define conditions for the experimenters' safe manipulation of the sample.

The neutron characterization of the tangential channel begins by measuring the neutron spectrum at its center ($y=0$) using the multi-foil activation technique. The measurement is described in [12], and the resulting neutron spectrum in $y=0$ is reported in Figure 8, where the results of different neutron spectrum adjustment codes are compared.

Figure 8: Neutron spectra obtained in the unfolding procedure using SAND-II (blue curve), STAYSL (green curve), and NLLSUP (black curve) codes and their comparison with the input trial spectrum from the MCNP simulation of the TAPIRO reactor in the middle position of the tangential channel.

The neutron spectra measurement in other positions of the tangential channel is planned for 2026. In the second phase, actinide samples will be irradiated in the positions where the neutron spectrum is known. The minimum and maximum actinide masses that can be inserted into the tangential channel were preliminarily investigated by performing an MCNP simulation of reactivity corresponding to different actinide masses. The maximum positive reactivity admissible by prescription in the tangential channel is 280 pcm and limits the maximum mass of Pu-239 at about 380 g. In Figure 9, the evaluation of reactivity inserted by a Pu-239 sample is reported. The minimum of about 2.5 g of Pu-239 introduces a positive reactivity comparable to the minimum reactivity measurable with the TAPIRO regulating rod, that is, about 1 pcm.

Figure 9: reactivity of the ^{239}Pu sample as a function of mass evaluated by MCNP. The maximum prescribed reactivity is reported as a dashed red line. The lower-right box shows the first few points and the lowest limit of measurable reactivity, indicated by a green line.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Reducing nuclear data uncertainty is a primary objective to be achieved for designing new nuclear reactors, as defined by several international expert groups. The ENEA TAPIRO research reactor was considered in this article to evaluate its contribution to nuclear data uncertainty reduction activities, in view of phase 2 of the AOSTA program. By applying methods such as sensitivity analysis,

representativity metrics, and covariance data evaluation, the study provides insight into the reactor's potential for targeted nuclear data validation. Results indicate that the TAPIRO reactor can serve as a valuable experimental platform for improving data on key nuclides such as U-235, U-238, Pu-239, Pu-240, among others listed in the HPR. These findings support the broader international effort to develop high-fidelity nuclear data that underpin reliable predictive modeling for Generation IV and other advanced nuclear fast systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors want to express their deepest gratitude to Mario Carta, who conceived and initiated this work during his career at ENEA, always striving to transfer his comprehensive knowledge to his collaborators and to emphasize the uniqueness and importance of having a reactor like TAPIRO available to the scientific community.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Falconi, V. Fabrizio, A. Santagata, "RSV TAPIRO and TRIGA RC-1 research reactors activities". *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, Volume 218, ISSN 0306-4549, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2025.111409>, (2025).
- [2] M. Carta, V. Fabrizio, A. Grossi, P. Blaise, B. Geslot, A. Gruel, F. Boccia, C. Bethaz, "Feasibility study of the AOSTA experimental campaign.", *EPJ Web Conference*, Volume 111, WONDER2015 - DOI: 10.1051/1107003 (2016)
- [3] A. Gandini, *Uncertainty Analysis and Experimental Data Transposition Methods Based on Perturbation Theory*, in *Handbook of Uncertainty Analysis*, Y. Ronen Ed., CRC Press, Boca Raton, Florida, (1988).
- [4] A. Gandini, *Generalized Perturbation Theory (GPT) Methods. A Heuristic Approach*, *Advances in Nuclear Science and Technology*, Vol. 19, J. Lewins and M. Becker Eds., Plenum Publishing Corporation, New York, (1987).
- [5] A. Gandini, M. Salvatores, I. Dal Bono, *Sensitivity Study of Fast Reactors Using Generalized Perturbation Techniques*, pp. 241-53 of *Fast Reactor Physics. Vol. I*, International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna, Austria, Oct. 1968.)
- [6] G. Rimpault et al., "The ERANOS Code and Data System for Fast Reactor Neutronic Analyses," *Proceedings of the PHYSOR International Conference*, Seoul, South Korea, (2002).
- [7] NEA Nuclear Energy Agency, JANIS, 2025. URL: https://www.oecd-nea.org/jcms/pl_39910/janis.
- [8] V. Fabrizio, et al., "Neutrons propagation in Lead: a feasibility study for experiments in the RSV TAPIRO fast research reactor", *EPJ Web of Conferences*, <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202328408006>, (2023).
- [9] C. J. Werner, et al, *MCNP User's Manual Code Version 6.2*. Los Alamos National Laboratory Tech. Rep. LA-UR-17-29981. Los Alamos, NM, USA. October 2017.
- [10] N. Burgio, L. Cretara, M. Frullini, A. Gandini, V. Peluso, A. Santagata, Monte Carlo simulation analysis of integral data measured in the SCK-CEN/ENEA experimental campaign on the TAPIRO fast reactor. Experimental and calculated data comparison, *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, Volume 273, (2014)
- [11] A. Plompen, "The Joint Evaluated Fission and Fusion Nuclear Data Library, JEFF-3.3," *The European Physical Journal A*, 2020.
- [12] L. Lepore, L. Falconi, V. Fabrizio, A. Santagata, N. Burgio, M. Cesaroni, B. Bianchi, P. Ricci, "IN-PILE FAST CALIBRATION OF ENEA TAPIRO TANGENTIAL CHANNEL NEUTRON SPECTRUM", *European Research Reactor Conference 2023 (RRFM) – ENS*, (2023)